

Guidelines for national and European KE plans & meetings (MS1)

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Work Package	1

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Abbreviations

AKIS - Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems

AMM - Adaptation and Mitigation Measures

AMP - Adaptation and Mitigation Plan

CDE - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

CFA- Climate Farm Advisor

CFD - Climate Farm Demo

CS - Climate Smart

CSF - Climate Smart Farming

EF - Experimental Farm

EU - European Union

GHG - Green House Gasses

KE - Knowledge Exchange

LF - Lighthouse Farm

M&E - Monitoring and Evaluation

NC - National Coordinator

NMU - Network Management Unit

PIPs - Projects, Flagship Initiatives, Policymakers

PDF - Pilot Demo Farm

R&I - Research and Innovation

TL - Thematic Leader

WP - Work Package

Abstract

The aim of the Guidelines for national and European KE plans & meetings is to support the TLs, NCs and CFAs in setting up and running their own networks, planning their knowledge exchange activities at national and EU level and preparing their KE plans, taking into account the specific requirements of the CFD project.

To give the reader a complete understanding, the guide starts with a brief description of the project and the purpose and use of the guide. To understand the role of the various stakeholders involved in the project, the guide introduces the purpose, structure, and members of the National Networks. We also present the KE at national and European level, including the main types of KE activities used in the project and offer a short methodological guide for their successful implementation. There is a comprehensive description of the organisation of annual national meetings and specific information on the first national meeting.

The document also includes templates to support the effective work of different stakeholders in planning, organizing and evaluating annual national meetings and in developing a national network plan.

The recommendations contained here can of course be adapted by each project partner to their own country, taking into account local circumstances and incorporating their own experiences.

1. Aim of this document and how to use it

The aim of this document is to **support the TLs, NCs and CFAs in building and running their own networks, planning their KE activities** on the national and EU level, and making their **KE plans**, with respect to the specific requirements of the CFD project. Sections 3 and 4 are mainly targeted to NCs and provide guidelines for KE on national level. Section 5 focuses on the guidelines for TLs to set up KE on EU level.

These Guidelines for national and European KE plans & meetings are a **user-friendly toolkit** which contains a collection of useful information, tips & tricks, schedules and templates for TLs and NCs. National KE plans will be updated 5 times (figure 1) during the project lifetime with current information for the next period, e.g., upcoming events, reports, activities.

Figure 1. Evaluation of national KE plans

How to use the guidelines?

At the beginning of the document, you will find a short overview of the project, as well as the objectives and purpose of this guide. This section will provide you with a context for understanding the significance of the guidelines and how they can support your project-related activities.

The third chapter (National Networks) introduces the purpose, structure, and members of the National Networks. It provides a detailed explanation of the criteria for different types of members, such as the responsibilities of National Coordinators, eligibility for Pilot Demo Farmers, and the role of Lighthouse Farms. Familiarize yourself with this section to understand the various stakeholders involved in the project.

The fourth chapter (KE on National Level) we present different types of knowledge exchange activities and offer a short methodological guide for their implementation. It includes a comprehensive description of organizing annual national meetings, and at the end of each chapter, we highlight specific information related to the 1st National Meeting. By thoroughly understanding this section, you will be well-equipped to plan and execute successful knowledge exchange events.

The chapter Knowledge exchange at the EU level gives information about the objectives, timeline and resources for successful KE on the European level. It contains detailed descriptions about the types of exchanges e.g. Annual cross-visit exchanges (xKEs), Twice-a-year thematic exchanges (T-KEs) and also specific planning for the TL kick-off session and the 1st xKE at 2AM in Cork.

This document also includes templates to support different aspects of your work. You will find templates for organizing and evaluating annual national meetings and developing a national network plan.

Templates for planning and evaluating annual EU-level KE plans will be disseminated at or soon after the 2AM in Cork, Ireland.

By familiarizing yourself with the contents of this guide, you will gain a comprehensive understanding of the project's KE objectives, the roles of various stakeholders, and the available templates.

2. About the project

Climate Farm Demo will strengthen European farmers' capacities to implement, demonstrate and uptake Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practice across the EU and reduce their GHG emissions along the project life thus achieving the EU 2030 Climate Target Plan. Therefore, Climate Farm Demo overall aims to first

1. network Pilot Demo Farmers (PDFs) to boost climate smart farming knowledge exchange and cross fertilisation among agricultural sectors and EU and national Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), then
2. support and advise Pilot-Demo-Farmers in implementing and demonstrating the Climate Smart Farming practices to increase innovation uptake and finally,
3. to incentivise the adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices across Europe thanks to standardized methodologies and relevant rewarding mechanisms that will support farmers in their systemic transition.

Figure 2. Climate Farm Demo in a nutshell

National networks (NN) will be formed in 27 countries. Building on the conceptual framework and the guidelines for how to set up a national network prepared in Task 1.2, Task 1.3 supports the development, implementation and evaluation of **annual national network plans and knowledge exchange** by National Coordinators. Knowledge exchange plans will build on input collected from all local actors during national annual meetings and will integrate the planned activities requested by WPs 1, 2, 3 & 8, and if relevant WP4-5-6.

Figure 3. Overall project structure and knowledge exchange

3. National networks

Climate Farm Demo works at the national level to involve key actors, such as PDFs and CFA, and stakeholders of the National CS-AKIS¹ in efficient knowledge exchange at farm, regional and national levels in national languages.

Each country establishes a network composed of sustainability-oriented farmers managing **Pilot-Demo-Farms (PDFs) and Experimental Farms (EFs)** linked to universities, research institutes and advisory services, and pioneering **Lighthouse Farms (LFs)** (see further for a [definition](#)). The table below shows the number of farms to be involved in the project per partner country.

¹ A Climate Smart Agriculture Knowledge & Innovation Systems (CS-AKIS) is a group of actors, stakeholders and organisations at regional, national or EU levels who join together to promote mutual learning, to generate, share, and use climate smart agriculture-related knowledge and information.

Emissions	Countries	Number of farms per country
Higher	FR, DE, ES, IT, PL, UK	130
Medium	IE, NL, RO, BE, DK, EL	60
Lower	AT, BG, EE, HR, LV, LT, LU, HU, PT, SL, SK, FI, SE, CH	25

National networks could be developed **on the base of already existing national or regional networks**, e.g., demonstration farm networks or other groups. If there is no such network to build on, network building can start from scratch. The national networks of PDFs will be consolidated in the first year of the project and linked-up together for knowledge exchange and cross-fertilisation.

3.1 Aim of the national networks

The NNs aim to:

- Enable their member PDFs and CFAs to exchange experiences and co-create new solutions on climate change, mitigation, emissions reduction, carbon neutral farm management, ecological footprint reduction
- Inspire new ideas to be taken up by farmers and by all other relevant actors
- Provide a platform for professional reflections

3.2 Structure

The national network will be structured as the following: multiple pilot demo farms (PDFs) are linked to a CFA in a regional/ thematic hub (Figure 4). Multiple hubs are linked on a national level to a National Coordinator. In some countries there will be only one hub, which will be a less complex structure.

Figure 4. Example of national network

3.3 Members of the national network

Active members/actors in the national network

National coordinators (NCs)

The NC is responsible for the Knowledge Exchanges (KE) at national level and for the Dissemination and Communication activities in his/her national CS-AKIS. The National Coordinators (NCs) run regular dissemination activities in their respective CS-AKIS. NCs will also be the main coordinators for CFD Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) per country. They will translate and contextualise the relevant DEC material for their country to ensure effective dissemination. National Coordinators will be the ambassadors of Climate Farm Demo in their countries for the press, TV and radio and will have a key role on developing links with policy makers and other CS-AKIS actors at national / regional level.

Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs)

CFAs are farm-advisors specialised in climate issues and adaptation and mitigation advise and operating at national/regional level. The CFA advises and regularly supports the PDFs in climate smart transition and in the organisation of demo-events. The CFA exchanges knowledge with other CFAs, all farms and all actors at national & EU level. CFAs from the 27 countries will be networked and trained annually over the life of the project to gain advisory methodological and soft skills, as well as climate-

smart technological knowledge, to properly guide the Pilot Demo Farmers along the journey. Furthermore, together with the NC, they will play an important role in the challenging endeavour to train and build capacities of PDFs on AMM, demonstration of best practices and rewarding mechanisms on annual basis during the national meetings. The pivotal role of the CFA in Climate Farm Demo has been specifically designed to facilitate the adoption of CSF practices.

Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs) represent 95% of the project 'farms. A PDF is a commercial farm managed by a sustainability-oriented farmer engaged in an innovation process and in demonstration activities. The PDF implements existing or new climate smart solutions and hosts on-farm demonstration towards "average farmers". The PDF exchange knowledge with other PDFs, EFs and LFs at national & EU levels.

Experimental Farms (EFs) are linked to universities, research institutes and advisory services. An EF is not a commercial farm and is managed by a R&I organisation with scientific & innovation purpose. The EFs act as training centre and national meeting place, organise demo events and experiment new solutions. The EFs exchange knowledge with other EFs, PDFs and LFs at national & EU levels.

Lighthouse Farms (LFs) are commercial farms managed by a sustainability-oriented farmer who test, innovate and implement new solutions: taking risk, acting as pioneer to pave the way of the future of farming. The LFs organise demonstration activities for PDFs and exchanges knowledge with other LF, PDFs and EFs at national & EU level. At least 1 exemplary LF will be labelled in each country. Read more about Lighthouse Farms in the [Lighthouse Farm Network Guide](#).

Other stakeholders in the national network

The main target groups of Climate Farm Demo are farmers, farm advisors, as well as economic and industrial actors of the value chains covered by the project. However, all actors and stakeholders identified and participating in the 27 national CS-AKIS are also important such as researchers, cooperatives, suppliers, agro-industry, EIP AGRI operational groups, other AKIS actors.

Researchers can co-create new solutions with a wide range of stakeholders engaged in sustainable transitions and increase multi-actor partnerships that accelerate the genesis of relevant CSF practices. Economic actors can benefit from participating in farmers networks and connect to a wide range of actors & stakeholders in the national AKIS. EIP Agri Service Point & CAP Networks accelerate knowledge exchange among the project and other AKIS actors and disseminate practical-oriented solutions, tools and methods and stimulate innovation partnerships in the European and national AKIS. Involving these AKIS actors in the project the impact and keeping them up to date about the insights generated in the project, the impact of the project on national level can be increased.

3.4 Added-value for national network members

The main benefit of participating in the national network is the possibility of connecting to other CS-AKIS actors and to take part in different knowledge exchange activities (e.g. peer to peer learning, training courses, farm demos, workshops) organised by the networks, where different actors can meet to discuss, learn, be trained and boost cooperation and impact. Besides this, participating in the national network offers the following specific benefits for different roles in the project:

Benefits for PDFs:

- To receive close support for free from a dedicated advisor for six years on climate mitigation and adaptation

- To improve technical aspects of your farm management, like herd management, crops, manure management, etc.
- To improve your farm efficiency, reduce operational costs, and reduce climate impact
- To be informed about funding opportunities and carbon-rewarding mechanisms
- To access applicable methods and tools for climate-smart practices
- To receive the latest research results and practical solutions produced in your region
- To participate in a six-year peer-to-peer knowledge exchange programme through cross-visits abroad and events in your region

Benefits for Candidate Lighthouse Farms:

- Candidate lighthouse farms will receive training on how to participate in Research and Innovation activities
- (Candidate) lighthouse farm will be part of a network of EU Climate Lighthouse farms and will be linked to a global network of lighthouse farms.
- When the Lighthouse Farms are selected in year 5, beautiful videos will be created about their stories to share on the website.

The benefit for the EFs:

- The support for the organisation of 2/3 demo events to share the findings from their ongoing experiments
- Use the CFD community to disseminate their research findings, receive feedback to their experiments from CFAs and Demo Farmers and engage fruitful discussion with the practitioners to better spread the on-going solutions to improve their relevance and impact
- Get better connected with the entire AKIS,
- Accelerate transfer to farmers, advisors and any AKIS actors

4. Knowledge exchange on national level

Within the CFD project, the following main types of knowledge exchange activities will take place on national level. The activities are planned annually for the following year at the annual national meetings (see template at the end of this document):

- Annual national meetings (one event per year, organized by NCs)
- Demonstration events (as separate events or connected to national meetings, [see](#))
- Cross visits (on-farm EU Cross-Visits will take place b2b with annual meetings as well as 2 times per thematic areas.)
- Workshops (as separate events or mainly connected to national meetings)
- Capacity building for advisors and PDFs (6-year program through peer-to-peer exchanges, training, and access to a Climate Smart knowledge repository)
- Training for PDFs, NCs & CFAs (as separate events or connected to national meetings)
- 1-on-1 meetings with PDFs (occasionally, as needed)
- National and EU thematic network meetings (organized by thematic leaders)
- Social network and chat applications (e.g. WhatsApp, Viber)

4.1 Activities of different actors in knowledge exchange

For detailed information on the different knowledge exchange activities in CFD, see the [Conceptual framework for network management and knowledge exchange on Climate Smart Farming](#). For information on on-farm demonstrations see [Design Guide for Climate Farm Demo Project On-farm Demonstrations](#)

More explanation for each of the activities mentioned here, are further explained in the next section:

National Coordinators (NCs)

- Organize national annual meetings
- Organize trainings for CFAs
- Organize trainings for PDFs
- Participate in trainings

Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs)

- Organize 1-on-1 meetings with PDFs
- Support the organization, facilitation and evaluation of demo events of the PDFs (three for each PDF over six years)
- Participate in training events related to farm demos and coach/support PDFs to increase their capacity in demo event delivery
- Participate in national and thematic network meetings
- Participate in trainings on national level
- Provide new information and knowledge gained through project activities to PDFs and other farmers (e.g. rewarding mechanisms available in their country, technical knowledge...

Pilot Demo Farms (PDFs)

- Host 3 demonstration events during the project
- Participate in national and, if possible and relevant, in thematic network meetings

(Candidate) Lighthouse Farms (LFs)

- Participate in network of exchange between selected (candidate) Lighthouse Farms and Global Network of Lighthouse Farms

Experimental farms (EFs)

- Organise demo activities on more innovative climate smart measures
- Participate in national and thematic network meetings

4.2 Main KE activities on national level

4.2.1 On-farm demonstrations

PDFs will carry out demo activities as part of the project. PDFs will implement existing or new climate smart solutions and host on-farm demonstrations towards farmers. Each farmer should host three demo

events over six years period, or a demonstration every second year. The total number of demonstrations per partner or per country will then depend on the number of farmers being supported.

On-farm demonstrations provide farmers with practical, tangible experiences of farming methods and technologies that they can use to improve their own farming practices. The demonstration farmers can play a key role through the provision of their practical insights concerning the new practice or technology. On-farm demonstrations must respect high quality standards in terms of organisation, implementation, facilitation and evaluation, to get the best out of peer-to-peer-learning effects, methods, experiences and networks.

You can find detailed information on on-farm demonstrations see [Design Guide for Climate Farm Demo Project On-farm Demonstrations](#)

You can find useful information, tips and tricks concerning demo practices on the "[Farm Demo](#)" website.

If a farm-based demonstration event is not feasible, e.g. geographical location (too far away from farmers), organisational difficulties, limited budget; or a topic that is better presented in an online format, virtual or hybrid demonstrations combining live and online formats may also be an option.

Virtual demo events and on-farm demo events share many similarities. Demo events are usually about showing and understanding innovations on a farm or in a local area. Virtual demo events have the same goal and exist in multiple formats, depending on their objectives (e.g. dissemination of knowledge, provision of advice and solutions, co-design of tools, research development). Virtual demonstration events can be classified according to the number of participants (from less than 10 to more than 200) and the level of peer-to-peer learning.

More information on virtual demonstrations can be found in the [FarmDemo Training Kit](#).

4.2.2. National annual meetings

Annual meetings in general

The most important things to know about organising annual meetings are outlined below. It is important to note that these are not "set in stone" expectations, but rather recommendations and suggestions to help you organise and run your meetings as efficiently as possible.

As the project partners are from countries of different sizes and with different farming systems and backgrounds, and as the number of PDFs in a country varies greatly (from 25 to 130 PDFs/country), it is clear that the meetings cannot be organised according to a single "template".

Although there will be some freedom in how to organise the annual meetings, there are some parts that are essential, see chapter *Expected outcomes and results*.

Since the number of participants can vary greatly from country to country, some partners may consider organising **several smaller events instead of one large one**. Due to the remote geographical location of farmers, the organisation of **on-line** or **hybrid meetings**, i.e., combining face-to-face participation with on-line participation, may also be an option.

As the first meeting is of particular importance for the participants to get to know each other and for further work together, information on this is also indicated in a separate section ([Guidelines for the first annual meeting](#)).

Objectives of the annual national meeting

The objectives of the annual national meeting are multifaceted. Firstly, it serves as a platform to bring together PDFs, CFAs, EFs, LFs and further AKIS members providing them with an opportunity to

- exchange ideas and experiences and knowledge
- evaluation of demo events and other national knowledge exchange activities (see *After the National Annual Meeting* form)
- plan national knowledge exchange activities for the next period (national KE plan)

Additionally, the meeting could be used to provide training depending on the agenda. Aim is to **enhance the skills and expertise of CFAs** by providing them with **annual training**, enabling them to better assist and support the PDFs.

The meeting can also be used as a way to **collect input and feedback from various local actors**, contributing to the **development and evaluation of annual national network plans**. The collaborative environment enables participants to jointly develop innovative climate smart solutions.

Who should be present on the meetings?

The annual national meetings are organized by the NCs in collaboration with the CFAs. While project partners/participants are naturally expected to attend, the scope of participation extends beyond them. The meetings offer a valuable opportunity for various actors within the AKIS to engage.

Participants expected to attend:

- Pilot Demo Farmers
- Climate Farm Advisors
- Experimental Farms and (Candidate) Climate Lighthouse Farms

Moreover, depending on the specific topics and focus of each meeting, NCs and CFAs can invite additional participants:

- Living lab participants
- Researchers
- Cooperatives, suppliers, agro-industry
- EIP AGRI operational groups
- Other AKIS actors

Venue of the event

The venue should be chosen where all the participants can be comfortably seated, coffee breaks can be arranged, and all the necessary facilities are available. It is essential to provide space for an active exchange of knowledge, e.g., participants should be able to move freely in a large room or work in small groups. If possible, the meeting should also be combined with a demo event to make it more attractive for PDFs and CFA, e.g., by organising the meeting on an experimental farm (or, if not possible, on a demo farm).

Suggested Agenda

The meeting provides a platform to address and discuss several relevant aspects, of which the evaluation of past year's activities and planning for next year is obligatory (marked in bold). These include:

- **evaluation and planning annual national network plans for KE** following a provided script (see annex)
- demo event
- trainings
- communication activities
- audits and reports

To facilitate productive discussions and engagement, various **facilitation methods** can be employed, such as **interactive workshops, group discussions, presentations, and knowledge-sharing sessions**. These methods aim to foster collaboration, encourage active participation, and ensure that the objectives of the meeting are effectively met.

Expected outcomes and results of the annual meeting

The meeting aims to yield several valuable outputs and results.

- It fosters exchange and reflection on new solutions related to climate change, adaptation to climate change, mitigation, emission reduction, carbon sequestration, carbon neutral farming, and ecological footprint reduction.
- Participating CFAs will acquire new and updated knowledge and skills, encompassing both technical expertise and soft skills, enabling them to provide better support to PDFs.
- PDFs gain technical expertise and soft skills, knowledge about farm demo activities and rewarding mechanisms.
- Cooperation between PDFs and living labs

Outputs to be produced during the meeting and to be included in the National Knowledge exchange plan:

- **Evaluation of past year's knowledge exchange activities (including demo events)** to be shared with WP1 and WP3 for overall learning on how to improve future knowledge exchange activities (See separate section [Evaluating CSF demo practices on a national level using the M&E tool.](#))
- The discussion held during the annual meeting will result in an **annual national network plan** for knowledge exchange (**indicative schedule of knowledge exchange activities for the year ahead**).

How to report on the annual meeting

Before the meeting, NCs are required to complete a pre-event survey by the end of September of each year on the back-office of the CFD website, so we can follow up that a meeting is scheduled. After each meeting, NCs are required to complete a short post-event survey, so we can follow up that the event took place. In addition, the NCs have to draft a national knowledge exchange plan based on the [template in annex](#). This plan will help NCs to monitor and follow up their national knowledge exchange activities. This plan has to be submitted by the end of December of each year.

Guidelines for the first annual meeting

Specific objectives of the 1st meeting

- Getting to know each other (PDFs, CFAs & NC)
- Focus on the role of the PDFs

- For the PDFs: learning about „the project essentials” – explaining audits, AMPs, and on-farm demonstrations (supporting a common understanding) + short intro on the overall network structure + project opportunities for them (becoming a lighthouse farm, capacity building (KE activities, training opportunities, ...)
- For the NCs/CFAs: learning about PDFs’ expectations, needs and concerns
- Discussing what climate change means for a given region/country, developing a common understanding. What will be the impact for farmers? What is the current impact of agriculture on climate change in the region/country? What will be the main challenges? How can we respond, what are the needs of PDFs and what should be the main strategies to meet these?
- Discuss how the network members would favour keeping in touch with one another, and how they would like to be kept informed of project activities.
- Summary of the discussion in the first (draft) knowledge exchange plan for the year ahead
- OPTIONAL (but strongly recommended): Experiencing a first demonstration

Participants of the first meeting

- PDFs
- CFAs
- NC

For the first meeting it is suggested to focus on the key actors, and not yet go beyond the above “core” group. The first meeting should support trust and cohesion in the PDF network and ensure that PDFs feel settled about their role in the project. This should be a moment to talk about expectations on both sides and clarify possible issues or questions. If the meeting is opened to other actors, this may hinder more opened discussions.

To build trust, it would be optimal for participants to attend the first meeting in person. For subsequent events, hybrid solutions are possible.

Suggested script for the first annual meeting:

- **Getting to know each other:** PDFs & CFAs use icebreaker methods (e.g., <https://www.sessionlab.com/blog/icebreaker-games/>; pick methods which are adapted to the size of your group, consider also working with breakout groups, e.g., by sector or region where the farmers are coming from; ask also for motivation to participate). Make sure to leave sufficient time for this.
- **General project introduction & climate smart farming (presentation)** with a focus on WP2 & WP3 (expectations from the project for PDFs) - to be followed by a facilitated discussion with the PDFs to address their questions, concerns and/or suggestions (again, decide on the format based on the size of your group: you can e.g. use online polling tools (Menti or other) for large groups or again work with smaller break out groups. Example facilitation methods:
 - <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/stinky-fish>
 - <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/world-cafe>
 - <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/i-expect>
 - <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/1-2-4-all>
- **Generating insights for a first draft of the national plan:** Jointly discuss what climate change means for your region/country and develop a common understanding. What will be the impact for farmers? What is the current impact of agriculture on climate change in the region/country? What will be the main challenges? How can we respond, what are the needs of PDFs and what should be the main strategies to meet these?

For starting a fruitful discussion on these topics, we suggest following group work and facilitation methods:

- Round Table Discussion / World Cafe Method: offline round table discussions can help to facilitate live exchanges. Set up a round table for participants and give each participant the opportunity to express their thoughts on climate change impacts, challenges, opportunities for action and their training needs. A facilitator should lead the discussion and take notes on ideas.
 - Inward Thinking: This is an offline group method that encourages participants to think about the topic on their own first before sharing their ideas with the group. At the beginning of the work, ask thought-provoking, possibly provocative questions for the group members to reflect on. The group can then collect and discuss the ideas.
 - Brainstorming: Set up a brainstorming session where participants can freely share their thoughts on how climate change affects them. The facilitator should encourage the free flow of ideas, record all ideas and then share them. Once the ideas have been collected, ask participants to group and classify them according to common themes or categories. This can help to organise the ideas in a more structured way.
 - SWOT analysis: analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. This technique can help participants identify the linkages and challenges between agriculture and climate change.
 - Short presentations: participants can be given the opportunity to give short presentations (3-5 minutes per person) to present their views, problems and ideas on climate change. The group can then discuss the presentations.
 - Lateral Thinking: using techniques developed by Edward de Bono, such as "six-cap thinking" or "creative action", which extend traditional thinking frameworks.
- **Introduction to on-farm, virtual and hybrid demonstrations:** provide an overview of on-farm demonstrations based on the information and insights gained from the training conducted during the annual meeting in Cork, including a brief presentation on the criteria for qualifying as an on-farm demonstration and guidelines for designing effective farm demos. Additionally, you can discuss the project's expectations for on-farm demonstrations, with the possibility of **combining the first meeting with an initial on-farm demonstration**.

A suggested agenda for the first national meeting:

Figure 5. Suggested agenda for the first national meeting

Additional ideas for the first meeting:

- **Expert presentations** on climate change research and innovations
- **Demonstration** of best practices - preferably on Experimental farm or PDF

Outcomes / results of the first meeting

PDFs attend the meeting and start working together. They are introduced to and understand their responsibilities and roles, and what the audit, AMP and on-farm demonstrations entails.

First draft of the national knowledge exchange plan: participants provide input for an initial draft of the knowledge exchange plan for the network's first year. This plan will outline the strategies and activities that will facilitate the sharing of knowledge and expertise among PDFs and other AKIS members.

Communication outputs: As part of CFD's efforts to disseminate information and raise awareness, participants will contribute to the development of various communication outputs. These will include writing a short press release, which will be distributed to media outlets, posting updates on social media platforms and develop articles tailored for agricultural press publications.

Evaluating past year's demo campaign and other knowledge exchange activities on a national level using the M&E tool

From the second national annual meeting onwards, the national annual meeting will be used to evaluate past year's knowledge exchange activities in the network, of which a majority will be demonstration events. Using a handout, the biggest focus will be to evaluate how to effectively demonstrate CSF practices. After this also other knowledge exchange activities will be evaluated.

Annual meeting script

In preparation of the National Annual Meeting

In preparation of the National Annual Meeting, the National Coordinator needs to prepare the Monitoring and Evaluation session. You can use the following checklist when preparing the meeting:

- Look up your country's main climate issue as defined during the first National Annual Meeting.
- Print out the M&E hexagon tool on A0 format or on multiple A4 formats if you are not able to print A0. (In case of virtual and hybrid meetings prepare a PowerPoint presentation.) The M&E hexagon tool can be found in *PDF format on the Sharepoint in the WP3 folder*.
- Collect post-its, pens, and other tools you think might be useful to carry out the M&E session.
- Prepare the M&E session using the script in the next section.

During the National Annual Meeting

National Annual Meeting				
Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning script				
Timing	What	How	Who	Materials
5 min	Introduction	<p>Introduce the ME&L tool and goal: <i>The overall goal off Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning in CFD is to improve the quality and impact of climate smart farming demo activities and to better plan other types of knowledge exchange activities in the national network.</i></p> <p>During the National Annual Meetings, we collect lessons learned about demonstrating Climate Smart Farming practices from each country participating in CFD.</p>	National coordinator	If you want, you can prepare a short PowerPoint, but it is not necessary for the process. If you do, keep it short and simple so most time can be spent on the collective evaluation of the past demo year
5 min	Explanation of ME&L tool	Shortly explain the group reflection process	National coordinator	National Annual Meeting M ME&L hexagon Tool, printed on A0 format
60 min	Group reflection on the past demo year	<p>Discuss the questions below, following the hexagon tool in a clockwise direction. For each question, you can ask each participant to first write their input on a post-it, put it on the hexagon tool and then discuss. <i>NB. If a large group is attending the meeting, split up the group in subgroups of around 10-15 people and ask them to fill in the hexagon tool in the subgroups.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fill in your country's main climate issue (as defined during the first National Annual Meeting). Have you defined multiple climate issues? Then you can choose 1 (e.g., based on preference or chose the most pressing issue) 2. Ask all CFAs and PDFs5 to provide 1 demo example(s): How did you demonstrate climate smart farming practices to tackle your national climate issue? Describe the example in detail, so this example can be used in other cases with the same climate issue. 	Facilitated by the national coordinator, input from CFAs and attending demo farmers	National Annual Meeting ME&L hexagon Tool, printed on A0 format or hand out multiple (A4) formats to sub groups Post-its, pens

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 highlight of the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that worked well for your country's climate issue. e.g., open discussion, professional facilitator, open workspace, field trip, etc. 4. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 main challenge in demonstrating solutions for the central climate issue during the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that were a challenge for demonstrating the climate issue. E.g., too many/less visitors, no clear goal, no real-life examples, etc. 5. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share what they want to improve in the coming year to build on successes and address challenges. This information will be used as a basis for new trainings and ME&L tools over the course of the CFD project. 6. Ask all CFAs and demo farmers what support they need to improve the Climate Smart Farming demos (skills, tools, etc.). 7. Ask all CFAs and PDFs if there is anything else they want to get off their chest. 		
25 min	Evaluation of other knowledge exchange activities	<p>Discuss the questions below, following 3 hexagons at the bottom of the template:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Give everybody 5 minutes to write down on post-its answers to the first 2 questions (each answer on a different post-it): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Which knowledge exchange activities (other than demo events) were successful according to you?</i> - <i>Which activities did you miss in the national network?</i> 2. Ask everybody one-by-one to provide their answer on the first question and ask each time if anybody else has written down the same or something similar. 3. Take a look at the answers to both first questions and discuss ideas for future national knowledge exchange activities to increase the project's impact. 		
5 min	Closing	Very shortly summarise the discussion and close the ME&L exercise		

After the National Annual Meeting

After organising a national annual meeting, it is important to collect all data for ME&L. It needs to be included in the template for the national knowledge exchange plan.

Questions from tool	Collected answers from annual meeting
Demo year highlights:	
Main challenges:	
Demo example(s) from your climate issue:	
Improvements for coming year:	
What do you need to improve the CSF demos?:	
To get off your chest:	

Handout – National Annual meeting

Figure 6. Handout for National Annual Meeting

Budget

Each participating country and national coordinator is granted autonomy in devising the structure and timing of the annual meeting according to their preferences and available resources.

Some examples of modalities for the annual meeting:

- **Online:** Hold the event entirely online. This allows participants to easily join virtual meetings, minimizing travel and accommodation costs.
- **Hybrid format:** Those who are close to the event location can attend in person, while others can join online. This method allows for face-to-face interactions while reducing travel costs.
- **Several small events:** Especially relevant in case of higher emissions countries with a larger number of PDFs. Organize multiple smaller events at the local or regional level within the same country. This enables participants to attend more easily while minimizing travel and accommodation expenses and room rental costs.
- **Combination with an existing event:** Link the annual meeting with an existing national or regional event that brings together the same community. This allows for the sharing of resources while minimizing costs. Good opportunity to share national activities and results.
- **Connect with existing or planned demonstration events:** Transform the meeting into an event linked to existing or planned demonstration activities. This provides an opportunity for practical demonstrations and sharing firsthand experiences.

These are just a few examples of possible meeting types. It is important for NCs to be inventive and organize the events within the basic guidelines (content and audience) provided.

4.2.3 Trainings for NCs and CFAs

National coordinators will be trained on project level (during online or general assemble meetings) and if relevant they are requested to repeat the training on national level for CFAs and/or PDFs. These trainings could be organised back-to-back with national annual meetings or on other occasions if more suitable. The main objective of trainings is to increase competences and knowledge of NCs and CFAs. For example, a training module on the organisation of on-farm demonstrations is developed and will be organised during the GA meeting in Cork. The participants there will be asked to repeat this training in their own country. They are able to use the produced materials and translate it to their own context.

Training and Capacity Building Flow

Figure 7. Training and capacity building flow

CFAs attend training events to gain the necessary skills and methods to support PDFs and increase their capacity to deliver demonstration events. National coordinators participate in trainings necessary to acquire the relevant skills to properly run their activities in the network. The technical training provides specialized thematic knowledge (e.g. mitigation plan, agricultural knowledge) while capacity building for gives methodological knowledge and soft skills needed to carry out their tasks.

Who will be the trainers?

Figure 8. Trainers of technical training and capacity building

4.2.4 One-on-one interaction between PDF and CFA

One-on-one coaching and consulting is commonly recognised as effective for addressing individual challenges in implementing new practices (Nettle et al., 2022). For a CFA it is important to get to know the PDFs he/she is supporting. It is recommended to target messages carefully, since different farmers can respond very differently to interventions (Rose et al, 2018). Therefore, CFA should identify well their audience, to understand their attitudes towards climate change, their values and their workflow. For

example, in some areas advisors specifically choose not to mention climate change to avoid creating distrust among farmers (Wreford et al. 2017). Nettle et al. (2022) mention the success of coaching models as advisory service. This advisory model works “*with farmers’ own knowledge and local context while supporting their autonomy, and coaches can operate as intermediaries between farmers and researchers (Cobon et al. 2021)*” (Nettle et al. 2022, p. K).

The **audit that will be done in each PDF in the second year of the project**, will be a great opportunity to get to know the PDFs. The audit should **not only focus on farm technical data, but also on behavioural aspects**, to gain insights in the attitudes and barriers of PDFs towards CFA. This might require some soft skills from CFA to discuss this matter with farmers.

The audit will form the basis for the adaptation and mitigation plan (AMP) that will be built together with the PDF. These AMP together with the audits, will form valuable input for discussion during demo events in the hubs.

Building a trust relationship between PDF and CFA is very important for a successful change process. Farmers tend to be quite critical to the person providing information. Nettle et al (2022) report that the effectiveness of one-to-one advice and thus the quality of knowledge exchange is dependent on the extent of **trust, credibility and empathy between farmer and advisor**.

Sutherland et al. (2013; in Nettle et al. 2022) found that building trust requires a long-term relationship between advisers and farmers. Similarly, Rose et al. (2018) emphasize the need for sustained engagement over time to maintain behavioral changes, as people often revert to old habits once the interaction ends.

Wreford et al. (2017) highlight the significance of how information about climate change is presented. They suggest that targeting information based on farmers’ values, without condemning other desirable behaviors, can lead to greater success. In general, people tend to respond better to positive, empowering messages that focus on gains rather than negatively framed messages that emphasize loss.

Another recommendation from Rose et al. (2018) for promoting behavior change is to demonstrate the value and ease of adopting new practices to farmers. It is crucial for farmers to perceive the benefits of adopting new behaviors, otherwise they may not be motivated to change. Therefore, we propose initially focusing on adaptation and mitigation measures that bring about improvements (or at least maintain the current state) in the farm system, particularly in terms of economic and labor aspects.

For detailed information on one-on-one meetings, see the [Conceptual framework for network management and knowledge exchange on Climate Smart Farming](#).

Practical ideas for 1-1 advice / interaction with PDFs

Ask questions and listen actively: start the meeting by asking the farmer questions and listening to his or her perspective, goals and challenges. This will help you to understand the farmer's needs and local circumstances.

- Personalised solutions: provide tailored advice and solutions based on the information and the farmer's needs. Consider the size of the farm, the resources available and the farmer's preferences.
- Concrete examples and demonstration: Use concrete examples and demonstration tools to illustrate practices or technologies that can promote climate-smart farming.
- Mutual cooperation: enable the farmer to actively participate in the extension process. Ensure that the farmer can ask questions and share his experiences and ideas.
- Targets and action plans. Create action plans detailing actions, timelines and resources and support farmers in achieving them. Focus on practical solutions that are well adapted to the farmer's situation and genuinely achievable; select a small number of achievable measures.
- Follow-up and feedback. Provide feedback to farmers on progress made and give further support or suggestions to improve the process.
- Local communities and networks: encourage farmers to join local communities or networks where they can exchange experiences and get new ideas from other farmers.

These ideas can help advisors to provide effective and tailored support to farmers in adopting climate-smart agricultural practices. It is important that communication is open, two-way and focused on farmers' needs and circumstances.

4.2.5 Group work

In order to run annual meetings and farm demos properly, it is useful if NCs and CFAs are aware of the basic features of group work. In the following we provide useful information and ideas.

Effective group work methods play a crucial role in fostering collaboration between PDFs, CFAs and other AKIS actors. Throughout the project, group work can be applied at various events, with the primary focus on national annual meetings, which bring together diverse groups with varying compositions and sizes, including the "core group" and also representatives from living labs, researchers, and other AKIS stakeholders. Facilitated by climate farm advisors or national coordinators, these group work sessions aim to promote the discussion of climate-smart solutions, information and experience exchange, brainstorming, and more.

Due to geographical distances and cost-effectiveness concerns, online group work sessions and meetings will also be conducted, particularly in larger countries.

Furthermore, group work is integral to farm demo events and study tours, which are outlined in the "Design Guide for Climate Farm Demo Project On-farm Demonstrations" (Document D3.1).

When planning group work, you should also consider the following factors:

Group Size

The choice of group size depends on the objectives of the demonstration and significantly impacts the event's format.

Smaller groups (8-15 participants):

- More effective for knowledge exchange, reflection, and deep peer-to-peer learning.
- Easier to manage, fostering a conducive environment for discussions.
- Closed groups that meet regularly tend to build trust, enhancing the quality of discussions.

Larger groups:

- Suitable for raising awareness and disseminating knowledge on a broader scale.
- Help to attract sponsors and farm supply companies.
- Require advanced audio-visual systems.
- Can be subdivided into smaller groups for focused discussions.

Group Types

A combination of various group types can be advantageous to comprehensively address different tasks and challenges:

Discussion Group/Study Group: Establish discussion or study groups where farmers and CFAs and other actors collaborate to exchange ideas, share experiences, and discuss advancements in smart climate farming methods. These groups foster knowledge sharing, peer learning, and mutual understanding.

Action Group/Task Force: Form action groups or task forces dedicated to implementing specific climate smart farming practices. Farmers and advisors collaborate to design, test, and implement innovative techniques aligned with local climate conditions.

Workshop and Training Groups: Organize workshops and training sessions for farmers, facilitated by CFAs. These sessions offer hands-on training in utilizing smart farming technologies and optimizing resource use while encouraging dialogues and problem-solving.

Support Group: Establish support groups for farmers (facilitated by CFAs) to discuss challenges related to climate change and climate smart farming methods. These groups offer emotional support, advice, and coping strategies for adapting to changing weather patterns and new agricultural practices.

Networking Group: Create networking groups that enable farmers and advisors to connect with other professionals in the agriculture and climate sectors. These groups foster collaboration, partnerships, and resource access, contributing to project success.

By strategically combining these group types, a comprehensive approach emerges that addresses knowledge sharing, practical implementation, emotional support, skill development, networking, and advocacy within the context of smart climate farming. This approach promotes collaboration between

farmers and advisors, enabling a holistic and effective co-creation for sustainable agriculture in the face of climate change.

Additional ideas for knowledge exchange methods for CFAs

- Information materials and case studies: Use the information materials provided by the CFD project and additional materials that illustrate the impacts of climate change on agriculture and the results that can be achieved by applying climate-smart practices. Provide examples of farmers who have already successfully applied these methods.
- Personalised advice. Then provide personalized recommendations for climate-smart farming practices, taking into account local conditions and farm specificities.
- Demonstration events: organise demonstrations where farmers can see and experience climate-smart practices in action. For example, demonstrate climate-friendly growing areas or climate-protection technologies and their benefits and effectiveness.
- Exchanges of experience and training: organise exchanges of experience and training for farmers, where they can meet professionals who have already successfully applied climate-friendly practices. This provides an opportunity for knowledge and experience exchange and mentoring between farmers.
- Emphasise economic or labour benefits: highlight the economic benefits of climate-smart agricultural practices, such as potential energy cost savings, efficient use of resources and long-term sustainability. Demonstrate the savings and long-term gains that these methods can bring to the economy.

It is important to be patient when giving advice and to tailor recommendations to the specific needs of farmers. Make communication personal and emphasise the long-term benefits of climate change responses for both farmers and the environment.

5. Knowledge exchange at the EU level

The role of **knowledge exchange in the EU level** is to support project activities via facilitated knowledge exchange encounters between international project partners. KE activities contribute to the wider CFD ambition to enable farmers' social learning and behavioural change, and to thereby facilitate an enabling environment for climate smart farming (see D1.1 Conceptual Framework) (Rose et al. 2018).

KE activities at the EU level are organized around **twelve themes** which connect actors across levels of the project (Figure 4). In addition, CFD includes seven sector themes which are transversal to the 12 specific themes; these are: organic, pigs, poultry, crops, fruits, vegetables, and protein and oil seed crops. Each theme is coordinated by a Thematic Leader (TL), who are the main parties responsible for organizing and enacting the KE activities, with guidance from the T1.4 partners.

Figure 9. The 12 thematic areas of climate smart agriculture practices covered in Climate Farm Demo

5.1 Objectives, timeline, and resources

The overarching objectives of the CFD knowledge exchange (KE) activities at the EU level are to:

- 1) **Connect** actors from across the project to each other around the 12 specific and 7 transversal themes;
- 2) **Exchange** knowledge between National Networks around common themes;
- 3) **Reflect** on and evaluate the progress of the project in relation to advancement of knowledge on the 12 themes and on the development of an EU network of Climate Smart Lighthouse Farms.

These objectives will be achieved through organizing two types of KE activities: **annual cross-visit exchanges** (xKEs) held in coordination with the annual meeting (AM), and **twice-a-year thematic exchanges** (T-KEs). Details and guidelines for each type of KE is explained in the following section. The first KE will be an annual cross-visit exchange at the second AM in Cork, Ireland in October 2023. Following this kick-off the KEs will progress following a regular schedule. *Figure 5* illustrates the timeline for the proposed KE activities over the course of the project. The general progression of KE content (both xKEs and T-KEs) will follow the framework for behavioural change outlined in the Conceptual

Framework document. Exact content focus of the KEs will be defined by the TLs as the project progresses.

Timeline of EU-level KE activities

Figure 10. Timeline of the proposed EU-level knowledge exchange activities. xKE = annual cross-visit exchange; T-KE = thematic exchange. General progression of KE content (both xKEs and T-KEs) may follow the framework for behavioural change outlined in the Conceptual Framework document (example topics added under T-KE events), but exact content focus of the KEs will be determined by the TLs as they deem appropriate.

TLs are expected to lead the organization and execution of the EU-level KE activities. Partners from T1.4 will be available to provide support, in particular at the annual cross-visit exchanges. Over the 7 years of the project, each TL has 6 PM for EU knowledge exchange; we expect TLs to spend 1 PM per year, starting in project year 2, on KE activities (organizing, hosting, attending, reporting, etc.). Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) each have 1 PM for EU knowledge exchange, which may be used to co-organize and attend KE events as appropriate.

In addition to KE meeting moments, TLs are recommended to organize their own internal organizational meetings every ½ year (once in person in coordination with the AM, and once online), in order to share tools and experiences and align content. A first meeting to stimulate this habit and introduce TLs to their responsibilities were held in Sept. 2023, coordinated by T1.4 partners and in collaboration with the TLs from the sister project Climate Smart Advisors (CSA).

5.2 Types of knowledge exchanges

Annual cross-visit exchanges (xKEs)

The objectives of the annual cross-visit KEs are to:

- 1) **connect** TLs to each other around shared topics and experiences;
- 2) **showcase** an existing Lighthouse Farm and/or a candidate Climate-Smart Lighthouse Farm;

- 3) provide a forum for multiple different types of project actors to **meet** and **share** ideas and knowledge on cross-cutting topics.

Timing: In tandem with or immediately following the in-person CFD annual meeting (AM), e.g. as the final (half)day in the meeting schedule

Frequency: Annually, beginning at the 2nd AM (October 2023)

Location: On-site at one of the current and/or candidate Climate-Smart Lighthouse Farms, if not possible then at a near-by farm

Target audience: TLs, , NCs, CSAs, invited farmers, anyone at the annual meeting

Organizers: TLs, with support of T1.4 partners

General guidelines for the organization of the xKEs include:

- The location of the meeting and position in the timeline of the project should jointly inform the thematic content of the meeting.
- The TLs are encouraged to use a bottom-up approach to decide on the content based on what is most relevant to their theme/region/farmers. A prototype method/activity for identifying and choosing content will be piloted at the TL kick-off meeting in Sept. 2023. Content should not focus on a single theme but address multiple and/or cross-cutting themes.
- In addition to technical topics, content may focus on cross-cutting theme(s) with relevance to the current stage of the project and may build year-to-year in relation to the stage of the project / learning process.
- The visit should include a farm visit with an integrative approach linking the farm visit to the thematic focus (tour, presentation by the farmers)
- The exchange should include an interactive component (e.g. workshop or other facilitated exchange activity). Emphasis should be on interaction, not lectures
- Program should include a reflection activity and evaluation of the last year's thematic exchanges, as well as planning for exchanges in coming year. T1.4 partners will provide guidance on how to structure the reflection and evaluation.
- Farmers who are invited to participate should be offered compensation for their time and travel, at the discretion of the TLs and National Coordinators.

Twice-a-year thematic exchanges (T-KEs)

In addition to the annual cross-visit exchanges, there will also be smaller-scale exchanges twice per year on the themes managed by the TLs. These exchanges should be held online to facilitate the participation of TLs and advisors in multiple countries. The objectives of the thematic exchanges are:

- 1) **connect** project members (NCs, CSAs, possibly farmers) across country- and region-specific networks around the connecting themes;
- 2) **exchange** more in-depth learning and technical knowledge within these specific themes.

Timing: At the discretion of the TLs

Frequency: Twice per year, beginning in 2024

Location: Online

Target audience: TLs, NCs, CSAs, possibly invited farmers (KE will be in English, which may be a limiting factor for some farmers), CFD project members (at the discretion of the TLs coordinating the event).

Organizers: TLs. It is strongly encouraged that webinars are jointly organized with the CSA project TLs.

General guidelines for the organization of the T-KEs include:

- TLs are responsible for organizing and facilitating the exchanges, driving the content, and identifying and inviting target participants.
- Exchanges should be focused on technical / practical topics as identified by the TLs, in alignment with the 12 specific themes and/or the 7 transversal/sector themes.
- Content decided by the TLs in response to needs and ideas of national coordinators and CFA, adapted to address thematic needs and issues as they emerge.
- First exchanges (first couple of years) should focus on individual themes. As interest / links between themes develop and emerge, in later exchanges 2-3 related themes can be grouped for cross-thematic exchanges.

5.3 Alignment with other CFD WPs and other projects

The Climate Smart Advisor (CSA) project will also be hosting KEs on the same 12 key themes. CFD TLs have had the opportunity to meet these TLs in a joint kick-off meeting in Sept. 2023, and are encouraged to align with them for cross-project exchanges at later stages in the projects. A selection of shared resources (including a complete TL contact list) will be shared with the TLs of both projects in order to align KE efforts.

The TLs will also be provided with the PIP inventory produced in WP7, which is categories by thematic area and can easily be searched by the TLs to find and align with other projects around common themes.

5.4 Evaluation of the KE plans and activities

At the end/beginning of each year, the past year's activities will be evaluated and the results from this evaluation will feed in a KE plan for the coming year. Guidelines for the evaluation will be provided by Task 1.6 in due time.

Addendum: Specific planning for 1st xKE at 2AM in Cork

Planning steps

1. T1.4 coordinators have met with the TLs online before the AM (September 13th 2023) to introduce the KE plan and clarify TL roles, and to generate first ideas for content for AM meeting. This was a joint meeting with CFD and CSA TLs. The main outputs of this meeting were:
 - a. TLs from both projects were introduced to each other
 - b. A first round of questions was collected which will become part of a working document on FAQs of CFD TLs.
 - c. TLs brainstormed ideas for T-KEs (topics, formats) and generated a first inventory of possible content connections between themes
2. At the AM, T1.4 coordinators will host a work session for TLs to harvest ideas for KE agenda for the coming year and begin drafting KE plans. This work session is open to all CFD AM attendees, with special focus on TLs, NCs, and CSAs.
 - a. Session will be 2 hours, with a carousel that each theme gets attention – all participants can contribute
 - b. We will make a summary of the ideas that came out of AM (building on the output of the TL kick-off meeting in Sept. 2023), and TLs will use this to set preliminary agenda for the coming year
3. Plan an online follow-up a few weeks after the AM with TLs to recap what came out
 - a. Ask TLs to deliver a final plan for 2024 on which type of activities they would like to do on their theme

Points of attention to address / be aware of in TL planning

- How to bring in learning on soft exchanges / incorporate behavioral change stages with technical topics and needs? Provide soft skills training and exchange, but also technical exchange on solutions for climate change adaptation and mitigation
- There will be different technical knowledge skills at each stage – set these as the topics to structure exchanges around
- How will we get the local experiences of the farmers to the EU level and be able to exchange upon it? Especially if they are not at the KE meetings.
 - o Cover this at the annual cross-visit exchanges?
 - o Farmers make videos and share with the advisors? Share videos as discussion tools at meetings, live testimonies of the farmers
 - o Make a proposal for ways this could happen – who / when do the examples get selected?
- At each annual reflection moment, continue to build up written tools and guidelines for the TLs in managing KEs (e.g. templates for planning, evaluating, reflecting, etc.)
- Provide the TLs support in general, keep it more open for what they could do, but leave it up to them to decide.

Rose DC, Keating C, Morris C (2018) Understanding how to influence farmers' decision-making behaviour: a social science literature review, report for the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board, supported by UEA Consulting Ltd.

Appendices

Appendix 1 Pre-event survey for national meetings

(to be completed by end of September of each year)

Aim of the template: to follow up on the organisation of national annual meetings.

The date of the scheduled national annual meeting should be added to the Calendar. To be filled out on the **CFD website** [back-office dashboard](#) by each NC or CFA before the annual national network meetings.

Meeting no. / year	
Basic data, organization	
Country	
Organizer	
Date (between October and December)	
Venue	
Meeting details	
(Draft agenda) of the meeting	<p>e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the main regional issues and problems related to climate change? • Developing KE plan for next period • Evaluation of demo and other KE activities • Reports on cross-visits • Reports on the work of other hubs (if relevant) • Other topics
Is time for the evaluation of the past year's activities included in the agenda?	Yes/no
Expected number of participants	
Target group / participants (Check all that apply)	NC CFA Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs) Experimental Farms (EFs) Lighthouse Farms (LFs) Living Labs Researchers Cooperatives, suppliers, agro-industry EIP AGRI operational groups Other AKIS actors

Appendix 2: Template: Design your own national meeting

This template is an aid and can be used by national coordinators to plan and prepare their national annual meeting, but it is not an obligation.

Practical information on the meeting

Location: ...

Date: ...

Time:

Objectives of the meeting

Sometimes it is useful to add sub objectives. You can have multiple goals in one meeting. Try to make them specific. Ask yourself the question why you are organizing this meeting and what you want to get out of it.

Main objective ...

Sub objective ...

Sub objective ...

Main objective ...

Sub objective ...

Result

Desired results of the meeting are:

1. ..
2. ..
3. ..

Participants and roles

Write a few lines to give a better view on the people you want or will be involved in the meeting and their roles:

- NC
- CFA
- Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs)
- Experimental Farms (EFs)
- Lighthouse Farms (LFs)
- Living Labs
- Researchers
- Cooperatives, suppliers, agro-industry
- EIP AGRI operational groups
- Other AKIS actors

Who is participating? Why are they involved in this meeting? Do they have specific roles or tasks in the meeting or in the project? What is the minimum you expect from the participants? Can you reach the goals with this group of participants? If not who is missing?

Invitation

Think about how you will invite your targeted participants? How can you attract them to come to your meeting? Why is it relevant for them? Use the information from goals and results. There is difference in an invitation via an e-mail, phone call or one to one meeting!

Content of the invitation:

When to send out the save-the -date? When to send out the agenda?

Which communication channels will you use?

Preparation

Here you list the items that have to be dealt with before the meeting. Think about:

- *Reservation of the room(s) (is the room suitable for the meeting you want to organize: how is the atmosphere, temperature and fresh air)*
- *Catering: food and beverages if needed*
- *Support technologies: Flipcharts, whiteboards, projectors, laptops*
- *Could it help to ask to participants to prepare before the meeting to provide input on specific aspects during the meeting?*
- *Practical information for participants*
- *Location & how to travel*
- *A concept agenda*
- *If people have specific tasks (e.g., a presentation) tell them about your expectations and time available for presentation and discussion*
- *Make actions specific with a deadline and a dedicated person (name)*

Make a detailed script for the actual meeting: Choose your methods related to goal/participants/result/ time/importance

Time	Section & Goal	Process methods & Materials	Who
	<p><i>First describe the part of the meeting, what are you going to do.</i></p> <p>Underneath, describe the goal of this part of the programme</p>	<p><i>Make clear what process methods and/or material you are going to use (consider the goal of this section and expected behaviour of participants)</i></p>	<p><i>Make people (including yourself) responsible for parts of the meeting and for reporting. This can also be participants in for example group discussions.</i></p>
12.30	<p>Arranging the room, flip-chats, light, beamer</p> <p>Goal: The room and the facilities are ready before the participants arrive</p>	<p>Which setting of the room makes the needed interaction most effective?</p> <p>Room setting plenary U-shape, beamer, screen, laptop, flipchart, markers. Room setting group work table and chairs for 6, flipchart, markers, ...</p>	
13.00	<p>Always be on time as facilitator and host</p> <p>Goal: a warm welcome for the participants</p>		
13.15	<p>Participants are arriving</p> <p>Goal: People do have time to settle in the meeting</p> <p>Workshop can start in time</p>	<p>Coffee/Tea/cake etc. on the table</p>	
13.30	<p>Welcome</p> <p>Goal: Importance of meeting is drafted</p>		

Time	Section & Goal	Process methods & Materials	Who
	<p>Introduction of the agenda and participants</p> <p>Goals and agenda are clear for participants.</p> <p>Participants get to know each other</p>	<p>Programme and goal on sheet or flipchart</p> <p>Are participants familiar to each other?</p> <p>You could make a round with an introduction question so they can link their personal situation/ambition to the goal of the meeting</p> <p>A more energizer method to get to know each other could work</p>	
	<p>Section related to sub objective ..</p>	<p>What input do you and/or participants have to bring here to realize the goal of this section? How to create a balanced input?</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Introduce the situation via a PPT and write down the central question on a flip chart;</p> <p>Let participants write their individual answers on post its and stick them on the flip chart;</p> <p>Cluster and reflect on it.</p>	
	<p>Don't forget breaks when meetings are long</p> <p>Goal: Participants can stretch legs, move around, and talk around</p>	<p>Can be used process as a moment to talk in small groups about a subject.</p> <p>Can be helpful in decision making and forming an opinion.</p>	
	<p>Section related to sub goal...</p>		

Time	Section & Goal	Process methods & Materials	Who
	Wrap up and closing the meeting Goal: The meeting clearly closed, participants can give feedback, participants are aware of the follow up from the workshop (including own tasks)	You may think of specific evaluation/follow up questions for participants with different roles	
17.00	Start drinks		
17.30	End meeting		

Make a detailed script for your meeting

Time	Section & Goal	Process methods & Materials	Who

Appendix 3 Post event survey for annual national network meetings

Meeting no. / year	
Basic data, organization	
Country	
Organizer	
Date	
Venue	
Meeting details	
Topics of the meeting	
Number of participants	
Role of participants in the project (Check all that apply)	<i>NC</i> <i>CFA</i> Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs) Experimental Farms (EFs) Lighthouse Farms (LFs) Living Labs Researchers Cooperatives, suppliers, agro-industry EIP AGRI operational groups Other AKIS actors
Meeting agenda	
Evaluate the event implementation: what went well, what could be improved? (max 350 characters)	

Appendix 4 Template for national knowledge exchange plan

National Knowledge Exchange Plan #[Add number]

Country:

Date: [add date of submission]

National Coordinator: [Name, Organisation]

CFA contributors: [Names]

Objective

The objective of the knowledge exchange plan is to provide a structured approach to develop activities that serve the national Climate Farm Demo networks. It helps to specify the networks' goals and to plan related activities to reach these goals. It helps to align all knowledge exchange and capacity building activities in a country and to work towards shared objectives. This document can then be used to monitor and evaluate the activities in organised in the national network.

The plans result from the discussion organised during annual meetings and monitoring of activities on the CFD website [back-office dashboard](#), to be integrated in this template. They will have to be update yearly and submitted by December of each working year, from 2023 onwards.

Climate impact

Describe here the current situation regarding climate change in your country based on the discussion during the national kick off meeting.

- *What does climate change mean in your country? What is the impact for farmers and how do agricultural activities impact climate change?*
- *What are or will be the main challenges in your country?*
- *Think about how you could link the CFD activities to other activities in your country.*

Answer:

Priority topics identified:

Existing expertise and initiatives

- *Which projects, initiatives, trainings, resources etc. do already exist in our country that are dealing with these topics?*
- *How could the CFD national network activities link and create synergies with these?*
- *What would be the knowledge needs of the farmers, advisors and other AKIS actors that your network activities could fill?*

Answer:

Where would you estimate the farmers in your country/region locate themselves in the adoption process regarding the topics put forward? Mark the stages that are most applicable for each priority topic. Repeat this for each priority topic defined.

PRIORITY TOPIC: [Add here the priority topic]		
Stage in behaviour change process of target audience		Knowledge need of farmers on this topic
1.	Farmers are not yet acknowledging a problem	<p>Building awareness on the effects of climate change and climate policy related to the topic.</p> <p>Making them aware about the importance to change their practices</p> <p>Gaining insights in the opportunities related to this topic. communicate the importance of change</p>
2.	Farmers acknowledge there is a problem, but are not yet ready to change	<p>Farmer need to be made aware about what is in it for them</p> <p>Farmers need to link the potential actions to their personal motivators</p>
3.	Farmers are getting ready to change	<p>They need demonstrations on the different climate solution and research innovations.</p> <p>They need support in deciding on the right adaptation and mitigation measures for their farms.</p> <p>Farmers need training and need to develop skills on specific adaptation and mitigation measures</p>
4.	Farmers are testing adaptation and mitigation measures	<p>Farmers need to share experiences with peers</p> <p>Farmers should co-create knowledge on specific climate issues and adaptation and mitigation measures.</p> <p>Farmers should be trained on how to implement climate policy and regulations</p>
5	Farmers are trying to maintain and grow the new behaviour	<p>Farmers need to be networked to farmers and other actors to strengthen cooperation and partnerships.</p> <p>Farmers need to debrief lessons learned.</p>

Goals & Strategies

Given the situation outlined above, think about what you want to achieve with your national CFD network in the coming year and what strategies you can use to achieve them. Specify the objectives, potential strategies (e.g. abovementioned initiatives to link with), the target groups, other actors to involve for the priority topics selected.

Based on the strategies revealed mentioned above provide a specific knowledge exchange action plan / program to be implemented for the next annual period. Include different kinds of activities such as demo events, trainings, workshops, national meetings, ... depending on the objectives and target group.

	Priority topic	Activity type <i>(demo event, national meeting, cross visit, training, capacity building, workshop, ...)</i>	Main objective of the event	Target group	Most suitable period	Potential location	Person / organization responsible for organization
1.							
2.							
3.							
...							

Challenges

Which challenges do you identify in the implementation of these strategies and how could they be anticipated?

Answer:

Evaluation of the national network activities

In the case of the first National Annual Meeting, this point is not relevant

The yearly activities will be evaluated on annual national meetings, and using feedback, the knowledge exchange plans will be refined for the following years. From 2024 onwards first perform the evaluation of the activities before adapting the national knowledge exchange plan.

Feedback on the evaluation of demo events	
<i>Please provide here the answers in English based on the completed ME&L tool as described in the guidelines</i>	
Demo year highlights	
Main challenges in demonstrating climate smart farming	
Demo example(s) from your climate issue	
Suggested improvements in demo organisations for the coming year	
(Project) support needed to improve the CSF demos?	
Feedback on the evaluation of other knowledge exchange activities	
<i>Please provide here the answers in English based on the completed ME&L tool as described in the guidelines</i>	
Description of successful knowledge exchange activities in the national network (that were not demo events) last year	
Which (type of) knowledge exchange activities were missed in the national network last year	
Suggestions for future national activities	

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